

D3.1 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	
UCs	Use Cases
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NPV	Net Present Value
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
ROI	Return On Investment
TEU	Twenty-Foot Equivalent Unit
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
PU	Perceived Usefulness
PEU	Perceived Ease of Use
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the development of a comprehensive evaluation framework to assess the impact of automation in multimodal freight transport. The objective is to establish a structured methodology for evaluating automation's effectiveness, efficiency, and broader implications, ensuring a robust and data-driven approach. The framework defines Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure automation's impact across various dimensions, including operational, economic, societal, environmental, safety, interoperability, and cybersecurity aspects.

The methodology follows a structured and iterative approach. It begins with a state-of-the-art analysis of relevant EU projects, identifying the best practices and evaluation methods. This analysis informs the selection of KPIs, which are chosen based on project objectives, grant agreement requirements, and input from project partners. The framework incorporates both qualitative and quantitative analyses to ensure a holistic assessment. The qualitative component is based on stakeholder perceptions and socio-technical factors, while the quantitative analysis relies on measurable KPIs to track automation's effects before and after implementation.

Additionally, this deliverable introduces preliminary approaches for assessing social impacts, conducting financial and economic feasibility analyses, and evaluating interoperability and cybersecurity concerns. These components will be further developed in upcoming project tasks (T3.3, T3.4, and T3.5).

A key feature of the framework is its ability to compare KPIs across different use cases, facilitating a cross-pilot evaluation of automation's impact. This comparative analysis enhances the understanding of automation's scalability and transferability across different logistics and transport scenarios.

Overall, this deliverable lays a solid foundation for assessing automation in multimodal freight transport. By integrating best practices, expert input, and a combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses, the proposed framework provides a reliable basis for evaluating automation's benefits, challenges, and long-term implications. Future project tasks will further refine and implement this methodology, ensuring a comprehensive assessment aligned with the project's objectives.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable

The objective of this deliverable is to develop an evaluation framework that provides a comprehensive foundation for assessing the impact of automation in multimodal freight transport. The framework will establish initial KPI measurements, encompassing both baseline and future scenarios, while identifying potential benefits and challenges associated with automation.

Our goal is to set up a clear and actionable methodology that project partners can follow during the execution of the project and implementation of the use cases. This methodology will guide the identification of the data required to measure KPIs both before and after automation is introduced, ensuring a robust evaluation of its impacts.

Furthermore, this deliverable lays the groundwork for the development of a complete evaluation and impact assessment framework. It defines the key elements to be evaluated, creating a structured approach to assessing automation's operational, economic, societal, and environmental impacts, as well as its implications for safety and cybersecurity.

1.2 Methodology

The development of the evaluation framework to assess the impact of Automation in Multimodal Freight Transport follows a structured and iterative methodology. The process starts with an initial assessment of European projects relevant to AutoMoTIF. Successively, we perform a state-of-the-art analysis of evaluation frameworks used in the selected relevant projects. This step allows for identifying the best practices and methodologies that could be adapted to the requirements of the AutoMoTIF project. In parallel, KPIs relevant to the assessment of automation are identified. These KPIs are extracted both from the AutoMoTIF Grant Agreement and by analyzing other relevant projects to ensure alignment with established standards with other European projects.

Subsequently, the main impact areas outlined in the AutoMoTIF grant agreement are identified, forming the foundation of the framework. These impact areas were further discussed and extended during the kickoff meeting and the first General Assembly (GA) meeting held in Bilbao. Through collaborative engagement with all project partners, the impact areas were refined to reflect a comprehensive and shared understanding of the project's objectives and challenges. Building on this initial refinement, further work was conducted as part of the preparation of D1.2 "AutoMoTIF Requirements and Benefits", which outlined the primary benefits and requirements for the defined Use Cases (UC). The insights from D1.2 were instrumental in deepening the understanding of the impacts, and the identified benefits and requirements were elaborated further to extract meaningful impact dimensions for the evaluation framework.

Therefore, the first step of the methodology involves defining and describing the areas of impact for automation in multimodal freight transport, specifically in maritime port operations. These areas of impact include operations, interoperability, economy, society, environment, safety, and cybersecurity dimensions.

This comprehensive categorization ensures that the evaluation framework addresses all critical aspects of automation, from its technical effectiveness to its broader implications for stakeholders and society.

The evaluation methodology introduces a preliminary proposal for supplementary analyses to provide a more comprehensive evaluation. These include an assessment of the social and environmental impacts of multimodal freight operations (scheduled for T3.5), a financial and economic feasibility analysis (planned for T3.4), and an interoperability and cybersecurity evaluation (to be conducted in T3.3). Each of these components is designed to complement the quantitative KPIs, ensuring a holistic understanding of project performance across multiple dimensions.

The evaluation framework itself consists of qualitative and quantitative analyses.

The qualitative analysis draws on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and socio-technical systems theory. TAM provides a foundation for assessing stakeholder perceptions of the usefulness and ease of use of automated systems, while socio-technical systems theory incorporates broader considerations such as social norms, trust in automation, ethical concerns, and workforce impacts. This qualitative approach ensures a holistic understanding of societal acceptance and stakeholder trust.

The quantitative analysis, on the other hand, is based on the measurement of KPIs. These KPIs provide objective metrics to evaluate specific aspects of automation's impact, such as operational efficiency, cost savings, environmental sustainability, and safety improvements. The quantitative component ensures that the evaluation framework is grounded in measurable and verifiable data, enabling robust comparisons across use cases and impact areas.

The methodology also outlines data needs and collection processes. Detailed guidance is provided within the framework on the types of data required, the sources for data collection, and the tools and methods for analysis. This ensures that the evaluation is supported by reliable and comprehensive datasets. A preliminary list of KPIs for each use case has been included in the framework, serving as a starting point for further refinement as the project progresses.

In summary, the development of the evaluation framework followed a systematic methodology that integrated inputs from state-of-the-art analyses, collaborative discussions with project partners, and insights from related deliverables. By combining qualitative and quantitative analyses and addressing the data requirements, the framework provides a robust basis for assessing the impact of automation in multimodal freight transport, ensuring that both technical performance and societal implications are comprehensively evaluated.

2 Analysis of Evaluation Assessment of Relevant European Projects

Evaluating the impact of technological and infrastructural innovations in logistics, mobility, and smart infrastructure is critical to ensure efficiency, sustainability, and scalability. Various European projects have developed distinct and complementary evaluation methodologies tailored to their specific objectives. This chapter synthesizes these methodologies, identifying common approaches, challenges, and best practices across multiple initiatives.

2.1 Relevant EU Projects

An online search was conducted to identify projects related to technological innovation in the transport sector, with special reference to multimodal freight transport automation. The focus was on projects that have published deliverables related to the impact assessment of the innovation within each project, measured through specific KPIs or qualitative research methods. The identified projects were then catalogued and organized according to their alignment with AutoMoTIF (High, Medium, Low), project status (Ongoing/Closed), and the online availability of the impact assessment deliverable.

In this way, an overall 45 projects were identified, out of which 13 were found to be relevant for a medium-high level, according to the criteria outlined above, as reported in the Table 1.

Table 1: European Projects closely related to AutoMoTIF

Project	Ongoing/Closed	Deliverable on Evaluation Available	Deliverable Name	Relevance of the Project Topic	Project Topic
5G-LOGINNOV	Closed 2023	YES	D1.4 Initial specification of evaluation and KPIs; Data collection and evaluation procedures.	HIGH	A new generation of terminals for value chain innovation. 5G creating opportunities for LOGistics supply chain Innovation.
COREALIS	Closed 2021	YES	D.6.1 Impact-assessment methodology for technical, operational and societal impacts and list of KPIs; D6.2 Final Impact Assessment and	HIGH	Port-centric technological and societal innovations

Project	Ongoing/Closed	Deliverable on Evaluation Available	Deliverable Name	Relevance of the Project Topic	Project Topic
			Evaluation Report.		
DOCKStheFUTURE	Closed 2020	YES	D3.1 Port of the Future KPI set.	HIGH	Ports of the future
MAGPIE	Ongoing - 2026	YES	Baseline evaluation and prioritization of demo-specific scenarios; Measurement requirements, method and KPIs framework.	HIGH	Making ports greener and smarter_sMArt Green Ports as Integrated Efficient multimodal hubs
MULTIRELOAD	Ongoing - 2025	YES	Evaluation of feasibility of multimodal transports along the Rhine-Alpine and Rhine-Danube-Corridor - v1.	HIGH	Alice is a partner. MultiRELOAD aims at developing “ Automated terminal operations ” through innovations and technologies for which results will be helpful for AutoMoTIF ambition
PIONEERS	Ongoing - 2026	YES	Detailed requirements for the assessment method	HIGH	Reducing greenhouse gas emissions in ports
PIXEL	Closed 2021	YES	D8.1 Evaluation plan	HIGH	Port IoT for Environmental Leverage
AEOLIX	Closed 2019	YES	D.6.1 Impacts monitoring, dynamic assessment and evaluation.	MEDIUM	Architecture for EurOpean Logistics Information eXchange
INTERMODEL EU	Closed 2019	YES	D8.3 Set of KPIs for assessing and operating intermodal terminals.	MEDIUM	The project aims to develop an integrated decision support platform to assess different pilot cases of Multimodal, Multiproduct and Multipurpose Freight Rail Terminals
MOSES	Closed 2023	YES	D7.1 Evaluation Pilot; D6.4 Evaluation	MEDIUM	Automated tugboat operations
SMART CM	Closed	NO	NA	MEDIUM	Improve efficiency, interoperability, and service quality in

Project	Ongoing/Closed	Deliverable on Evaluation Available	Deliverable Name	Relevance of the Project Topic	Project Topic
					container transport chains
Compass4D	Closed	NO	NA	MEDIUM	Road safety, efficiency, and reduce congestion
FREILOT	Closed	YES	D.FL.4.1 Evaluation Methodology and Plan	MEDIUM	Energy efficiency in urban road goods transport

Table 1 summarizes key European projects, highlighting their evaluation methodologies and relevance to automation, logistics, and sustainability. The availability of deliverables on assessment frameworks and KPIs underscores the collective effort to enhance efficiency, environmental performance, and technological integration in multimodal transport and port operations. These insights contribute to the development of robust evaluation strategies for future projects.

2.2 Evaluation Frameworks: Insights from Similar Projects

This section provides a concise overview of selected European projects, focusing on their evaluation methodologies. It highlights key assessment frameworks, metrics, and best practices used to measure project impact, offering insights into their applicability to the current study.

The AEOLIX project enhances supply chain data visibility through a secure, cloud-based collaborative ecosystem, integrating multiple stakeholders and enabling efficient logistics management. Eleven regional Living Labs assess its impact using a two-tier evaluation based on the FESTA framework, measuring business advantages and dynamic market adoption through KPIs.

The 5GLOGINNOV project develops a framework for integrating and validating Connected Automated Driving/Mobility (CAD/CAM) technologies within Industry 4.0 and port environments, aligning with 5G-PPP themes. It evaluates technical, operational, environmental, and societal impacts through quantitative and qualitative methodologies, ensuring scalability.

Compass4D improves road safety and efficiency by deploying cooperative ITS services in seven European cities, implementing Road Hazard Warning (RHW), Red Light Violation Warning (RLVW), and Energy Efficient Intersection (EEIS). Its evaluation follows the FESTA methodology, employing a city-specific matrix to assess driver behavior changes and performance indicators before and after implementation.

COREALIS focuses on port-centric innovations within five Living Labs, utilizing KPIs to assess technical, operational, environmental, economic, and societal impacts, with three evaluation pillars: operational and technical assessment, future port operations, and societal impact in a port-city context. It employs

predefined scenarios to align user requirements with system specifications, using functional and non-functional testing for system validation.

DocksTheFuture defines the "Port of the Future" vision for 2030, addressing digitalization, emissions reduction, and renewable energy. Its KPI set follows the World Ports Sustainable Program (WPSP), covering climate and energy, governance, infrastructure resilience, and security, with interdependencies ensuring multiple project objectives are considered.

FREILOT enhances urban goods transport energy efficiency by integrating traffic, fleet, and driver performance management. Its evaluation, based on FESTA methodology, assesses fuel consumption, emissions, traffic efficiency, and driver acceptance, providing insights into the AEOLIX framework.

INTERMODEL EU evaluates intermodal terminal performance through a KPI set developed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), incorporating expert interviews and multi-criteria decision-making methods. MAGPIE accelerates green energy adoption in port operations through nine demonstrators, measuring environmental, operational, and socio-economic impacts via a KPI-based impact assessment. MOSES improves Short Sea Shipping (SSS) by addressing large containership challenges, evaluating its logistics matchmaking platform's efficiency, sustainability, and modal shift using categorized success indicators.

MULTIRELOAD fosters greenhouse gas-neutral shipping and multimodal transport along key corridors, conducting feasibility studies based on qualitative assessments of infrastructure, regulations, and transport nodes.

PIONEERS, led by the Port of Antwerp, collaborates with European ports to reduce emissions while maintaining competitiveness, using literature reviews, expert interviews, and categorized performance indicators across operational, tactical, and strategic levels.

PIXEL promotes voluntary data exchange between ports through a structured evaluation of technical performance, interoperability, and economic impact, utilizing the FESTA methodology for KPI definition and impact measurement.

SMART-CEM enhances container transport chain efficiency through technological advancements, evaluating operational, technical, and socio-economic impacts using quantitative and qualitative methodologies, confirming its potential for supply chain improvements and policy recommendations.

2.3 FESTA based Evaluation Methodologies

Several projects, including AEOLIX, Compass4D, FREILOT, PIXEL, and SMART-CM, have leveraged the FESTA (Field Operational Test Support Action) methodology as a foundation for their evaluation frameworks. This approach involves defining research questions, hypotheses, and performance indicators to assess both technical and operational impacts.

AEOLIX, for example, employs a two-tier assessment model within its Living Labs to evaluate business advantages and market adoption dynamically. Similarly, Compass4D and FREILOT assess driver behavior, fuel consumption, emissions, and efficiency improvements using an evaluation matrix customized for each test environment. PIXEL extends this methodology to analyze ICT infrastructure interoperability and usability, while SMART-CM evaluates operational and socio-economic benefits in supply chain management.

2.4 KPIs Evaluation

Projects such as DOCKSTHEFUTURE, COREALIS, MAGPIE, and PIONEERS focus on KPI-driven evaluation frameworks, ensuring alignment with strategic objectives like environmental sustainability, efficiency, and economic feasibility. DOCKSTHEFUTURE categorizes KPIs according to the World Ports Sustainable Program (WPSP), incorporating SDG-aligned metrics for climate, governance, and resilience.

COREALIS evaluates technical, operational, environmental, and societal impacts across multiple ports, while MAGPIE's assessment framework emphasizes emissions reduction, operational efficiency, and socio-economic KPIs. PIONEERS refines these indicators through expert interviews and categorizes them into operational, tactical, and strategic levels to guide decision-making.

2.5 Quantitative and Qualitative Hybrid Approaches

Projects such as 5GLOGINNOV, INTERMODEL EU, and MULTIRELOAD employ a combination of quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods to assess the feasibility and scalability of innovative logistics solutions.

5GLOGINNOV aligns with 5G-PPP thematic and applies both quantitative and qualitative measures to analyze connected mobility applications. INTERMODEL EU adopts a multi-criteria decision-making approach, using an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to determine KPI relevance in intermodal freight terminal operations. MULTIRELOAD extends this concept by analyzing technological and infrastructural conditions along European transport corridors, incorporating legal and regulatory assessments to identify barriers to multimodal transport adoption.

2.4.1 Real-World Impact Monitoring and Validation

AEOLIX, MOSES, and PIXEL emphasize dynamic impact monitoring and real-world validation. AEOLIX employs real-time market adoption tracking using predefined KPIs across its Living Labs. MOSES focuses on evaluating multi-modal transport effectiveness through Success Indicators (SIs) categorized into technical, societal, market, and economic dimensions. PIXEL further refines real-world validation by structuring assessments around technical, business, and economic impacts, incorporating future R&D considerations.

2.4.2 Common Themes and Best Practices

This section highlights the key evaluation methodologies and best practices emerging across various projects. By examining the approaches used in initiatives within the logistics, mobility, and smart

infrastructure sectors, we can identify recurring themes that contribute to robust, scalable, and sustainable innovations. The following bullet points summarize these common practices:

- **Living Labs and Real-World Testing:** Several projects, including AEOLIX, COREALIS, and MAGPIE, utilize Living Labs to validate their methodologies within real-world environments. This approach enhances scalability and ensures practical feasibility.
- **Stakeholder-Centric Evaluation:** INTERMODEL EU and PIONEERS engage industry experts and decision-makers in refining evaluation criteria, improving relevance and accuracy.
- **Sustainability and Societal Impact Considerations:** DOCKSTHEFUTURE, MAGPIE, and PIONEERS incorporate environmental and socio-economic dimensions, aligning their evaluation frameworks with broader sustainability goals.
- **Scalability and Transferability:** 5GLOGINNOV, MULTIRELOAD, and SMART-CM assess scalability and intermodal transport feasibility, ensuring solutions can be adapted across different contexts.
- **Technology-Driven Innovation Assessment:** Projects like FREILOT, MOSES, and PIXEL focus on testing the interoperability and effectiveness of new technologies, such as cooperative ITS services, logistics matchmaking platforms, and voluntary data exchange solutions.

The diverse evaluation methodologies across these projects demonstrate a shared commitment to enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and scalability in logistics, mobility, and smart infrastructure. By integrating FESTA-based assessments, KPI-driven frameworks, hybrid qualitative-quantitative approaches, and real-world validation mechanisms, this chapter presents a unified evaluation framework applicable across multiple domains. Leveraging these best practices can facilitate informed decision-making, promote policy alignment, and accelerate the adoption of transformative innovations in the European transport and logistics ecosystem.

3 Analysis of KPIs from Relevant Projects

3.1 KPIs from other EU projects

In this section, we present a detailed overview of the most relevant KPIs employed in the European projects that we have identified as closely related to AutoMoTIF. These KPIs have been carefully selected based on both their purpose and methodology, and they are organized by specific impact areas to facilitate a structured and comprehensive evaluation.

Each table below categorizes the indicators according to their respective domains—such as operational efficiency, environmental sustainability, safety, economic performance, and societal impact—providing a clear framework for understanding how performance is measured across different aspects of the projects. The tables offer concise summaries that include the KPI descriptions, the metrics used, and the data required for their evaluation.

Furthermore, these KPIs have been thoroughly considered by the Use Cases (UCs) during the selection process to ensure that the most appropriate and effective indicators are applied.

3.1.1 Impact Area: Economy

The Table 2 offers a detailed overview of KPIs sourced from projects like PIONEERS, DOCKSTHEFUTURE, COREALIS, and others. These KPIs, all categorized under the Economy impact area, are designed to measure various aspects of financial performance and efficiency.

Indicators range from generalized costs, turnover, and profitability metrics such as NPV, IRR, and ROI to time and cost savings. The table also includes operational KPIs like container cost per unit transported, throughput, and vehicle maintenance metrics that emphasize predictive maintenance. This overview serves as a strategic tool for evaluating the net benefits and economic impact of innovative projects across the European transport and logistics ecosystem.

Table 2: Economic KPIs from European Projects Relevant to AutoMoTIF

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
PIONEERS	Economy	Generalized costs	To incorporate the actual benefits or detriments generated with the implementation of an innovation, the generalized cost method will be utilized.
PIONEERS	Economy	Turnover	Can be defined as the amount received for sales in a stated period (year).
PIONEERS	Economy	Net Present Value (NPV)	The NPV can be defined as the present value of future cash flows at the project's required rate of return compared to the investment
PIONEERS	Economy	Internal Rate of Return (IRR)	The IRR can be defined as the rate at which the project breaks even.
PIONEERS/ NREMODEL EU	Economy	Return On Investment (ROI)	ROI can be utilized to assess the net profits or losses of the investment (t=x) compared to the initial investment (t=0).
PIONEERS	Economy	Time savings	Represents all the time savings that can be derived from implementing an innovation
PIONEERS/ DOCKSTHEFU TURE	Economy	Cost savings	Represents all the cost savings that can be derived from implementing an innovation
COREALIS	Economy	Container Cost per Unit transported (€/TEU).	measures the cost associated with transporting one Twenty-Foot Equivalent Unit (TEU) container over a certain distance or during a specific period. It is calculated by dividing the total cost of container transport (including logistics, handling, and operational costs) by the number of TEUs transported.
PIONEERS/ PIXEL/ INTERMODAL EU	Economy	Throughput	The number of tons or TEU handled by the port.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
5G- LOGINNOV	Economy	Parts in Stock; Vehicle Breakdowns Vehicles Under Maintenance Vehicles Unexpected Breakdown Maintenance Costs of Vehicles	Reduce total cost of spare parts and tires annually by at least 10%; Reduce maintenance costs of yard trucks by enhancing monitoring and predictive maintenance of port assets collecting telemetry data from different sensors equipped on yard trucks in port Operations. 5G connected trucks transmit telemetry data from sensors installed on yard trucks. The transmitted data will be used by the AI/ML algorithm to anticipate eventual breakdowns that lead to higher costs when handled with corrective maintenance or routine maintenance.
DOCKSTHEF UTURE	Economy	Estimated losses prevented	Computation (in euros) of the financial losses prevented by a specific action that lowers the risk of the downtime of port facilities.

In conclusion, this table presents a comprehensive set of economic KPIs that capture the financial and operational benefits of innovative projects in the European transport and logistics sector. These indicators enable data-driven decision-making by clearly quantifying cost efficiency, profitability, and maintenance improvements.

3.1.2 Impact Area: Environment

Table 3 presents key environmental KPIs from European projects relevant to AutoMoTIF. These indicators focus on assessing and reducing the environmental impact of transportation and logistics activities. By tracking emissions, fuel consumption, energy efficiency, and waste reduction, these KPIs provide insights into the effectiveness of sustainability measures in the sector.

Table 3: Environment KPIs from European Projects Relevant to AutoMoTIF

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
5G- LOGINNOV/CORE ALIS/DOCKSTHEF UTURE	Environment	Reduction of CO2 emission in single mode	Reduction of CO2 emission in single mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Environment	Reduction of CO2 emission in platoon mode	Reduction of CO2 emission in platoon mode with equipped vehicles.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
MAGPIE	Environment	CO2 per unit of transport activity	Reduction of CO2 emissions per unit of transport activity, where transport activity is defined as a unit of goods (tons, m3, TEU, etc.) carried over a unit of distance (km). This KPI monitors GHG emission intensity related to GHG efficiency of transport solutions
MAGPIE	Environment	CO2 per transshipment	Reduction of CO2 emissions per unit of transshipment, where transshipment is defined as a unit of goods (tons, container, TEU) that is transshipped at the port. This KPI monitors GHG emission intensity related to GHG efficiency of port transshipment activity.
MAGPIE	Environment	Emissions of other pollutants (NOx, SOx, PM2.5, PM10)	Reduction of other pollutant emissions. These performance indicators evaluate the emission of a specific pollutant (NOx, SOx, PM2.5 or PM10) per unit of transport activity, where transport activity is defined as a unit of goods (tons, m3, TEU, etc.) carried over a unit of distance (km).
DOCKSTHEFUTURE/MAGPIE	Environment	Reduction of emissions in ports (noise, air, water,)	Reduction of negative externalities of the port's operation that have an impact on the local community.
5G-LOGINNOV	Environment	EPI - cl per ton and km' for vehicle trips	Optimize energy performance index 'EPI - cl per ton and km'.
5G-LOGINNOV	Environment	API 'KWh per ton and km' for vehicle trips	Optimize acceleration performance index 'API - KWh per ton and km'.
COREALIS	Environment	Per crane power consumption	Measure overall and per crane power consumption
DOCKSTHEFUTURE	Environment	Waste reduction (plastic, dredging material)	The amount of any natural resource that re-enters the economic cycle can be expressed in its respective quantity. To simplify comparison, processed materials should be traced to a related basic resource.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
5G-LOGINNOV/MAGPIE/AEOLIX	Environment	Fuel Consumption	Reduction in the fuel consumption of trucks (average) in port operations by minimizing truck waiting times, e.g., at port gates, at container handover operations
5G-LOGINNOV	Environment	Fuel consumption in single mode	Reduction of fuel consumption in single mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Environment	Fuel consumption in platoon mode	Reduction of fuel consumption in single mode with equipped vehicles.
INTERMODEL EU	Environment	Carbon footprint per TEU	Reduction of carbon footprint per TEU.
INTERMODEL EU	Environment	Energy consumption per TEU	Reduction of energy consumption per TEU.

The environmental KPIs in this table serve as essential metrics for evaluating the ecological footprint of transport operations. By focusing on reducing emissions, optimizing energy consumption, and improving resource efficiency, these indicators contribute to a greener and more sustainable mobility and logistics ecosystem.

3.1.3 Impact Area: Operations

Table 4 consolidates a comprehensive array of operations KPIs drawn from various European projects relevant to AutoMoTIF. This table details performance indicators that span a wide range of operational domains—including autonomous vessel and container handling, terminal processes, and vehicle performance metrics. Each KPI is accompanied by a description and the necessary data inputs, providing a clear framework to evaluate operational innovations and improvements across multiple pilots and project implementations.

Table 4: Operations KPIs from European Projects Relevant to AutoMoTIF

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
MOSES	Operations	N. 15 KPIs related to Autonomous Tugboats innovation	Indicators identified to evaluate innovations linked to Pilot 1 of the project
MOSES	Operations	N. 15 KPIs related to Autonomous Docking System innovation	Indicators identified to evaluate innovations linked to Pilot 1 of the project
MOSES	Operations	N. 11 KPIs related to Innovative Feeder Vessel innovation	Indicators identified to evaluate innovations linked to Pilot 2 of the project
MOSES	Operations	N. 7 KPIs related to Robotic Container Handling innovation	Indicators identified to evaluate innovations linked to Pilot 3 of the project
AEOLIX	Operations	Consolidated trips	Increase in consolidated trips. It measures the efficiency and optimization of transportation activities, especially focusing on the movement of goods or containers between the port and other locations (such as warehouses, distribution centers, or inland terminals).
AEOLIX/COREALIS	Operations	Average loading/unloading time	Reduction of average loading/unloading time of vessels.
COREALIS	Operations	Average operation execution time (by the forklift).	The average time it takes to complete a specific operation.
MAGPIE	Operations	Lead time freight	Reduction of the time that is needed to move a shipment from start to end location within the demo. This KPI monitors the time that it takes to complete physical operations that are within the scope of the demo. All other things being equal, the shorter Lead Time is, the better.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
COREALIS/INTERMODAL EU	Operations	Vessel turnaround time	To measure the efficiency of port operations in handling a vessel from the moment it arrives at the port to the moment it departs. This KPI tracks the time spent in port, accounting for all activities involved in preparing the vessel for its next leg of the journey.
COREALIS	Operations	Time for gate-in/out operations (average, max, ...).	Time is necessary to complete in/out operations at the gate.
COREALIS	Operations	Truck waiting time inside the terminal.	It measures the amount of time trucks spend waiting within the boundaries of a terminal. This includes any delays caused by administrative procedures, congestion, or waiting for available loading docks or equipment. A higher truck waiting time can indicate inefficiencies in terminal operations.
COREALIS	Operations	Truck waiting time outside the terminal.	It measures the amount of time trucks spend waiting outside the terminal, typically before they are allowed to enter or are assigned a loading/unloading dock. Long truck waiting times outside the terminal can signal inefficiencies in the scheduling system, poor traffic management, or insufficient capacity at the terminal's entrance.
COREALIS	Operations	Number of slots per hour	It refers to the number of available time slots for trucks, containers, or other vehicles that can be assigned for specific activities (such as loading, unloading, or port entry) within an hour. This KPI is used to gauge the capacity of a terminal, warehouse, or facility to handle operations efficiently.
COREALIS	Operations	Number of bookings per hour.	Number of reservations or appointments made for specific activities (such as truck arrivals, container handling, or cargo processing) within an hour.
COREALIS	Operations	Vessel idle time at berth.	It refers to the time during which a vessel is moored at the berth without carrying out any productive activity, such as loading or unloading cargo. It is an important indicator for measuring the efficiency of port operations and optimizing the use of berths.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
5G- LOGINNOV/CORE ALIS	Operations	Time Trucks Parked in the Area	Measure the amount of time spent by tracked vehicles in fully stopped mode (engine off), to determine overall efficiency of use of vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Truck Speed	Measure the average vehicle speed during vehicle operations.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Truck Acceleration	Measure the vehicle acceleration, based on the information collected from the CAN bus, as well as the GNSS module inside the IoT device. This information can serve as an input in improving driving style (with positive impact on fuel consumption), as well as in determining dangerous driving behavior.
COREALIS/INTERM ODAL EU	Operations	Occupied space during the cargo storage phase.	It indicates the percentage or total volume of available space that is occupied by goods, containers, or other cargo. This KPI helps assess the efficiency of space utilization within the facility. High occupancy rates may indicate that the facility is effectively using its storage capacity, while low occupancy could suggest underutilization of space.
COREALIS	Operations	Optimize stacking height and location of container stacks	It measures how efficiently containers are stacked and positioned to maximize storage space, minimize handling time, and improve operational efficiency.
COREALIS	Operations	Lifts/hours per crane.	measures the number of lifts (or movements) performed by a crane per hour of operation. A "lift" refers to the action of a crane picking up or placing a container or load. The KPI helps assess how effectively a crane is being utilized during its operational hours.
COREALIS	Operations	Number of terminals that reduced the number of handlings	In the context of port or terminal operations, "handling" refers to the physical movement of containers or cargo between different locations (e.g., from ship to dock, dock to storage, or storage to truck). Reducing the number of handlings is crucial for improving efficiency, lowering operational costs, and minimizing potential damage to goods.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
COREALIS	Operations	Cargo registration completion time.	Time needed to complete the cargo registration process.
5G-LOGINNOV/COREALIS	Operations	Vessel Operation Completion Time	Reduce vessel operation completion times by at least 5%. The developed computer vision model will automatically detect the presence/absence of container seals at the unloading/loading phase of vessels, alleviating (or minimizing) human personnel intervention (which consumes a considerable amount of time), hence, significantly accelerating the vessel operation completion time.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Average truck speed in single mode	Increase the average truck speed in single mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Average acceleration activities in single mode	Reduction of acceleration activities in single mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Stillstand time in single mode	Reduction of stillstand time in single mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Average truck speed in platoon mode	Increase the average truck speed in platoon mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Reduction of average acceleration activities in platoon mode	Reduction of acceleration activities in platoon mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Reduction of stillstand time in platoon mode	Reduction of stillstand time in platoon mode with equipped vehicles.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Percent of Empty Containers Runs	By counting the number of non-full arrivals (20ft) at PCT.

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
5G-LOGINNOV/INTER MODEL EU	Operations	Mean time of container job	Based on the real time ETA (estimated times of arrival) of external trucks, reassign Straddle Carriers (SCs) to either external or internal container jobs.
5G-LOGINNOV	Operations	Model Inference Time	Time to analyze each image. Using 5G will allow higher band width, so the transmitted images will not need so high compression rates, which will lead to easier compression / decompression algorithms and lower global inference times for each image.

In summary, the KPIs presented in this table offer a robust and detailed framework for assessing the operational efficiency of innovations within the European transport and logistics sector. These indicators enable stakeholders to track enhancements in processing times, resource utilization, and overall operational performance, ultimately supporting data-driven decision-making and continuous improvements in multimodal terminal operations.

3.1.4 Impact Area: Security/Safety

Table 5 presents key Security and Safety KPIs from various European projects that are relevant to AutoMoTIF. These indicators focus on improving workplace safety, monitoring unauthorized access to risk areas, and enhancing surveillance technologies. By leveraging advanced detection models and real-time data, these KPIs aim to minimize occupational hazards and security risks in logistics and transport operations.

Table 5: Security and Safety KPIs from European Projects Relevant to AutoMoTIF

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
DOCKSTHEFUTURE	Security/Safety	Reduction in fatal and non-fatal occupational injuries	The quantity of fatal and non-fatal casualties as reported.
5G-LOGINNOV	Security/Safety	Model accuracy/reliability for detection of people/vehicles non authorized in risk areas.	Ratio of success of the computer vision model for detection of people/vehicles not authorized in risk areas. This ratio will consider false positives, false negatives and true positives, using for this evaluation a set of annotated images that will be considered as

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
			the ground truth. The use of 5G will allow the transmitted images to have a higher quality, which will be reflected in a greater precision of the detection model, comparing with the previous schema.
5G-LOGINNOV	Security/Safety	Model accuracy/reliability	Accuracy of the vehicle counting and vehicle model detection. Tools: Novel surveillance technologies and mechanisms (drone-based, wearable cameras, AI/ML based video analytics)
COREALIS	Security/Safety	Number of gate incidents	Number of incidents at the gate.

The KPIs outlined in this table provide a structured approach to assessing and enhancing security and safety within transport and logistics environments. By integrating innovative surveillance technologies and data-driven safety measures, these projects contribute to safer and more secure operational processes across multimodal transport systems.

3.1.5 Impact Area: Society

Table 6 presents key Society KPIs from European projects that are relevant to AutoMoTIF. These indicators focus on assessing social acceptance, governance transparency, workforce diversity, and overall societal impact. By measuring public perception, employment generation, and community engagement, these KPIs help evaluate how transport and logistics innovations affect the broader social environment.

Table 6: Society KPIs from European Projects Relevant to AutoMoTIF

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
DOCKSTHEFUTURE/COREALIS	Society	Port acceptance	A representative and balanced sample of the port city's population may be surveyed and asked to which extent they value the port's impact on the community on an ordinal scale ranging from "positive" to "negative".
MAGPIE/PIXEL	Society	Social acceptance	According to the MAGPIE framework, were identified four categories of Demos Priorities: Sustainable mobility; Port-City Interface; Energy transition and circular economy; Biodiversity

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
			The scope is to develop a new framework to consider social dimensions involved in MAGPIE technologies implementation and reveal shapes of socio-technical acceptance related to the demos.
DOCKSTHEFUTUR E/PIXEL	Society	Degree of transparency in port governance	Evaluation to which extent the port authorities' processes, decision making and overall governance meet the aspects of traceability and transparency.
DOCKSTHEFUTUR E	Society	Share of women in upper management of port-based enterprises	The share (in %) of women in the executive and supervisory board of port-related businesses according to the corporation's statement
COREALIS	Society	Increase the engagement and satisfaction of employees.	How effectively a company is fostering a positive work environment, it may include measures like employee surveys, retention rates, productivity levels, and feedback on work culture and management
COREALIS	Society	Increase the engagement and satisfaction residents	Measuring how well a community or local authority is meeting the needs of its residents, enhancing their quality of life, and encouraging active participation in community activities or decision-making. It may include satisfaction surveys, participation in community events, or feedback on services like healthcare, safety, and public amenities.
PIONEERS	Society	Delta external costs	The culmination of the different external costs defined in the tactical performance indicators (i.e., noise pollution, air pollution, water pollution, light pollution)
PIONEERS	Society	Net positive effect on the social environment	Monetary quantification of the impact on the social environment (i.e., delta labor costs, delta employment)

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
MAGPIE/PIONEERS /INTERMODEL EU/DOCKSTHEFUTURE	Society	Number of jobs generated because of the project/innovation (demo)	The employment that is generated because of the demo. Analyzed by means of the number of jobs that are directly and indirectly involved in or created thanks to the demo. This includes both temporary and permanent jobs. The application scope needs to be defined, meaning what falls within the monitoring scope of this KPI: what are the activities that are part of the demo and need to be considered? The scope of the employment KPI should overlap with the scope of the other indicators, otherwise it is not possible to make suggestions about the impact.
MAGPIE/INTERMODEL EU	Society	OPEX	The operational expenditure (OPEX) is recurring expenses during normal business operations. The expenditures are part of the day-to-day operations, such as salaries, maintenance, and rents. The operating expenses can be both fixed and variable.
MAGPIE/PIONEERS /INTERMODEL EU	Society	CAPEX - sum of the capital expenditures	The capital expenditures (CAPEX) are in most cases long-term expenses in physical goods and property. These expenditures present how much a company/demonstrator is investing in existing and new fixed assets. The objective of capital expenditure is to generate future benefits and long-term value. The CAPEX KPI will be based on an overview of expenditures per demonstrator.
MAGPIE	Society	Spatial impact	Land Use is intended as the overall spatial footprint that the technology installations of the different Demos have once installed in the operating site, on both shore and seaside. This KPI monitors both the spatial impact in terms of area surfaces and volumes occupied by physical encumbrances. In addition, this KPI monitors the surface extent and territorial spread of networked structures, understood as physical connections, grids or plants.
5G-LOGINNOV	Society	Human resource optimization (person hours)	Computer vision assisted with surveillance of high-risk areas for automatically detecting human presence. Physical staff (appointed safety/security personnel) will no longer be needed for the service at the specified area(s). High resolution video of the selected area(s) is additionally streamed at PCT backend system

Source of KPI	Impact Area	KPI NAME	KPI description
INTERMODEL EU	Society	Congestion at the road gates of the terminal (added time to terminal users and passer-by)	Measure/reduce the congestion at the gate

The KPIs outlined in this table provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the societal implications of transport and logistics projects. By focusing on public acceptance, labor impact, governance transparency, and human resource optimization, these indicators support a more inclusive and socially responsible approach to innovation in the European mobility and logistics ecosystem.

4 Evaluation Framework

This chapter outlines the evaluation framework, which integrates both quantitative and qualitative analyses to assess project performance. We begin by describing the key impact areas identified during the second General Assembly in Bilbao. These impact areas are described based on the findings presented in D1.2 AutoMoTIF Requirements & Benefits, as well as insights gathered from the state-of-the-art analysis in previous chapters. Based on these Impact Areas and on the State-of-the-Art analysis presented in the previous chapter, the UC participants have selected the quantitative KPIs.

In addition to the quantitative metrics, this chapter introduces a preliminary proposal for the additional analysis. These include an Interoperability and Cybersecurity assessment (to be carried out in T3.3), a financial and economic feasibility assessment (planned for T3.4) and an evaluation of the social and environmental impacts of multimodal freight operations (scheduled for T3.5). Each of these components is designed to complement the quantitative KPIs, providing a holistic view of project performance across multiple dimensions.

Finally, the chapter introduces the quantitative analysis and details the KPI template, which serves as a standardized format for recording and reporting performance data. This template is explained in the following section, ensuring consistency and clarity in how KPIs are captured and analyzed.

Overall, this evaluation framework establishes a robust basis for performance measurement within the AutoMoTIF project, ensuring that all relevant impact areas are thoroughly assessed.

4.1 Defining and Describing Key Impact Areas

The evaluation framework identifies key impact areas that need to be assessed to fully understand the consequences automation will have. These include **Environmental Impact**, where the framework measures how well automation aligns with societal values on sustainability, and **Economic Impact**, which evaluates the perceived economic benefits of automation in comparison to its implementation costs. **Safety and Security Impact** are also critical, focusing on public trust in the ability of automated systems to reduce accidents and enhance security within transport networks. Additionally, **Operational Efficiency** is examined, looking at how automation improves the logistics process, such as reducing delays, optimizing resource use, and increasing throughput. Lastly, the framework evaluates **Society**, ensuring that automation benefits are distributed fairly across society and that job displacement is mitigated by appropriate reskilling initiatives.

4.1.1 Evaluating Environmental Impacts of Automation

The evaluation of environmental impacts in multimodal freight transport automation focuses on assessing how advanced systems and technologies contribute to sustainability within port operations. Automated systems play a pivotal role in reducing emissions and optimizing resource use throughout the logistics chain. The ability to calculate the most fuel-efficient routes across multiple transport modes allows for precise measurement of fuel consumption reductions. Evaluators examine how automated routing

minimizes unnecessary fuel usage and reduces overall emissions. Similarly, shipment consolidation, enabled by automation, is evaluated for its effectiveness in decreasing empty miles and preventing fuel waste.

Another critical area of evaluation is the integration of cleaner technologies, such as electric vehicles (EVs), hydrogen-powered trucks, renewable-energy-powered rail systems, and their adoption within automated logistics workflows. Metrics such as the reduction in fossil fuel dependency and the percentage of renewable energy used in operations provide insights into sustainability advancements. Evaluators also assess the role of strategically placed automated intermodal hubs in reducing long-distance trucking and increasing reliance on energy-efficient rail and sea transport, highlighting their impact on emission reductions.

To measure emissions, evaluations focus on the deployment and functionality of real-time sensors in autonomous vehicles and automated hubs. These sensors track key indicators such as fuel consumption, carbon emissions, and vehicle efficiency. Data collected from these systems is analyzed using digital twins and logistics platforms to assess overall environmental performance. Further evaluations consider the effectiveness of software tools in calculating the carbon footprint of transport legs and their ability to generate transparent, regulation-compliant emission reports aligned with standards like ISO 14064 or the GHG Protocol.

Forecasting capabilities are also evaluated, particularly the use of AI to predict emissions based on planned logistics activities. This aspect is assessed for its ability to inform proactive measures that further reduce environmental impacts. By examining these elements systematically, the evaluation framework ensures that the implementation of automation in port freight logistics contributes meaningfully to sustainability goals while providing measurable insights into its environmental performance.

4.1.2 Evaluating Safety Impacts of Automation

The evaluation of safety impacts in multimodal freight transport automation focuses on how automation enhances workplace safety, minimizes risks, and addresses challenges related to liability in automated systems. Automation plays a significant role in reducing the risk of accidents by minimizing worker exposure to hazardous situations. For example, automated systems handle high-risk tasks such as cargo handling, vessel berthing, and equipment operation, reducing direct human involvement in potentially dangerous environments. Evaluators assess the reduction in accident rates and analyze how automation improves overall workplace safety.

A key aspect of evaluation is the enhanced control and supervision of access to restricted areas within terminals. Automated access control systems, combined with surveillance technologies, ensure that only authorized personnel enter high-risk zones, thereby reducing the likelihood of incidents. The effectiveness of these systems can be assessed by monitoring access breaches and their subsequent impact on safety.

Automation also introduces advanced predictive maintenance systems to detect and prevent mechanical failures. By continuously monitoring equipment's health and performance, automated systems can identify potential failures before they occur, ensuring timely interventions and preventing accidents caused by

malfunctioning machinery. Evaluators examine the frequency of mechanical failures, the accuracy of automated detection systems, and the reduction in downtime caused by such issues.

However, automation also introduces complexities in determining liability in the event of accidents or incidents involving automated systems. Evaluators must consider how effectively these systems can log operational data, enabling a clear understanding of the sequence of events leading to an incident. This includes assessing the robustness of automated logging and reporting tools to ensure transparency and accountability.

By systematically evaluating these aspects, automation's impact on safety within multimodal freight transport can be quantified. This approach ensures that automation not only reduces risks but also establishes frameworks for accountability and further enhances safety standards in port logistics operations.

4.1.3 Evaluating Impacts on Operations of Automation

The evaluation of operational impacts in multimodal freight transport automation focuses on how automation improves service efficiency, reduces operational delays, and enhances decision-making and precision in cargo handling. One of the key operational benefits of automation is the optimization of port and shipping services. Automated systems enable better coordination across different transport modes, such as rail, sea, and road, leading to more streamlined operations and reduced waiting times at key nodes within the logistics network. Evaluators assess how automation improves the flow of goods between different modes of transport, reducing delays and improving overall port throughput.

Automation also drives enhanced operational efficiency, allowing terminals to operate at higher capacity with fewer resources. Automated systems, such as automated cargo handling and vessel berthing, minimize the time required for various processes and increase the overall productivity of port operations. The evaluation examines metrics like cargo turnover rates, turnaround times for vessels, and the reduction in operational downtime, comparing the performance before and after automation.

A crucial outcome of automation is the reduction in waiting times, both for vessels and trucks. Automated scheduling and coordination systems improve the timing of port arrivals and departures, allowing for faster loading and unloading of goods. Evaluators focus on tracking waiting times for vessels and trucks, identifying how automation reduces delays and accelerates the overall logistics process.

Additionally, automation results in faster and more efficient cargo handling. The ability to handle larger volumes of goods in less time contributes to smoother port operations and faster transit times for goods in the supply chain. Evaluators assess improvements in cargo handling speed, tracking KPIs such as time per unit of cargo and the number of containers handled per hour.

Improved decision-making is another critical operational benefit of automation. The integration of real-time data from sensors, automated systems, and digital platforms allows for more informed decision-making. Automated systems provide operators with real-time insights into port operations, enabling better resource

allocation, scheduling, and coordination. The evaluation framework tracks how the use of data analytics and automated decision-making tools enhances operational outcomes and reduces human errors.

In relation to cargo handling, automation improves precision in cargo movements, reducing the likelihood of human errors and minimizing cargo damage. Automated systems allow for more accurate tracking and handling of containers, minimizing the risk of misplacement, loss, or damage. Evaluators assess the improvement in cargo handling accuracy by tracking the rate of cargo damage before and after automation implementation, as well as measuring improvements in handling efficiency.

The use of automated systems also significantly enhances cargo traceability. With integrated tracking systems and sensors, cargo can be monitored at every stage of the transport process, providing real-time updates to stakeholders and improving transparency. The evaluation examines how automated systems improve traceability, focusing on factors such as accuracy of location tracking, data integrity, and the ability to share real-time information with stakeholders in the supply chain.

However, the more complex design and implementation of automated solutions presents challenges that must be considered in the evaluation. The process of designing and deploying automation systems can be intricate and resource-intensive, requiring significant planning, testing, and integration with existing infrastructure. Evaluators focus on assessing the complexity of implementing automated solutions, including the challenges related to system integration, infrastructure upgrades, and the coordination between different stakeholders involved in the automation process.

By evaluating these operational impacts, the benefits and challenges of automation in multimodal freight transport can be effectively measured, providing valuable insights into how automation enhances efficiency, precision, and decision-making while also considering the complexities involved in implementation.

4.1.4 Evaluating Interoperability & (Cyber)-Security Impacts

In the context of the project, interoperability and cybersecurity represent two fundamental impact areas that require a structured yet adaptable evaluation methodology. Given the diverse nature of the UCs involved, it is imperative to establish a comprehensive framework that ensures consistency in assessment while allowing for flexibility to accommodate the specific characteristics of each case. This section outlines the methodological approach to evaluating these two critical aspects, ensuring that all UCs adhere to a coherent strategy while considering their unique operational requirements.

Interoperability, within the scope of automation in supply chains, is understood as the seamless integration of diverse systems. This integration can be assessed from multiple perspectives, including the interoperability between different modes of transport and the connectivity of various management and information systems among stakeholders. From a technological standpoint, it is essential to evaluate how effectively different components interact, particularly when dealing with varying automation levels, distinct communication protocols, and heterogeneous infrastructures. Ensuring interoperability means guaranteeing that systems work harmoniously to facilitate efficient, automated operations.

Cybersecurity, on the other hand, encompasses all measures aimed at mitigating risks to the confidentiality, availability, and integrity of information. The evaluation of cybersecurity within the project follows two primary approaches. The first focuses on assessing the susceptibility of a system's network configuration to cyber threats, analyzing potential vulnerabilities and the exposure of communication infrastructures to attacks. The second approach shifts the focus from prevention to resilience, evaluating the extent to which security breaches impact operational performance and how effectively the system can recover. Rather than solely measuring the ability to prevent cyberattacks, this evaluation emphasizes the system's capacity to maintain continuity and restore normal operations with minimal disruption. A robust cybersecurity framework must therefore integrate both proactive defenses and reactive strategies that ensure rapid response and recovery in the face of potential threats.

Considering the intricate level of complexity of these impact areas, the evaluation methodology incorporates both quantitative and qualitative assessment techniques. Whenever feasible, use cases will prioritize a quantitative evaluation, leveraging measurable indicators to assess the performance and robustness of interoperability and cybersecurity mechanisms. In cases where direct quantification is not viable, a structured qualitative approach will be implemented, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the impact areas. By ensuring alignment with overarching project definitions of interoperability and cybersecurity, this methodology provides a robust and scalable approach that accommodates the specific needs of each UC while facilitating comparability and coherence across the entire project.

This methodology serves as the foundational guideline for all use cases to structure their evaluation efforts, ensuring a rigorous and coordinated assessment of interoperability and cybersecurity within the broader framework of automation.

4.1.5 Evaluating Economic and Financial Impacts

The evaluation of economic impacts in multimodal freight transport automation focuses on how automation boosts operational efficiency, economic growth, and presents both opportunities and challenges. Key benefits include increased scalability, enabling the transport network to handle more goods without proportional cost increases. Automated systems improve supply chain efficiency and flexibility, enhancing terminal capacity and reducing congestion.

Automation also generates significant time and cost savings, speeding up tasks like cargo handling and vessel berthing, leading to faster turnaround times and reduced operational costs. By optimizing labor, machinery, and infrastructure usage, automation reduces resource requirements, improving efficiency. Evaluators assess these factors through metrics such as unloading times, personnel reduction, and machinery use.

Additionally, automation optimizes asset and equipment management, reducing idle times and improving asset utilization. Evaluators track equipment scheduling and usage rates compared to manual operations. However, the transition to automation may cause delays and production losses, which the evaluation framework considers, including integration delays and workflow disruptions.

Training personnel to work with automated systems is costly and time-consuming, but the long-term benefits, including improved efficiency and reduced reliance on manual labor, are also evaluated. By assessing these factors, the economic impacts of automation on scalability, cost-effectiveness, and performance in port and terminal logistics are comprehensively understood, highlighting its role in sustainable growth and operational efficiency.

The potential impact of automation will be evaluated under an economic, business and financial lens in the context of T3.4: Financial and economic feasibility. The objective will be to assess the feasibility of implementing in real-life conditions, the automated processes that will have been developed and tested in simulated environments for all the AutoMoTIF use cases. Moreover, this task includes the identification and analysis of additional potential externalities associated with the deployment of automation, which could affect the use case study or/and any stakeholders involved.

There are different approaches met in the literature on how to perform the evaluation of financial and economic feasibility in the transport and logistics sector. For instance, the EU project AVENUE developed a tool which allows calculating the economic impact of implementing autonomous vehicles into existing transport networks and which can also perform valorization of different deployment scenarios (Antoniali et al., 2021). Ongel et al. (2019) employed a total cost of ownership (TCO) analysis per passenger-km to compare the costs of autonomous electric microtransit vehicles to those of traditional buses, using acquisition, operating and end-of-life costs. Jović et al. (2020) on the other hand, investigated the economic aspects of the following three automation innovations: maritime transport chain solution, vessel estimated time of arrival solution and delivery planning solution, using SWOT analysis. An economic feasibility study based on a life-cycle analysis is the selected approach of Khan (2025), with a focus on electric-connected automated vehicle shuttles, while addressing uncertainties in costs and revenue estimates. It is worth mentioning that a recent working paper (2024) by researchers of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), concluded that the economic impact of one major part of automation, Artificial Intelligence, is still quite vague and unclear, although tentatively vast (Comunale and Manera, 2024).

In AutoMoTIF, a structured approach will be followed to achieve the overarching goal of T3.4, which has been described above. Initially, any economic and financial data generated in the context of simulation tasks will be gathered and relevant KPIs will be established. Following that, the expected investment costs in automation will be compared against potential savings in different components such as labor, energy and operations. The readiness of businesses to adapt to automation, considering regulatory and other constraints will also be assessed, and an initial investment analysis to explore potential funding sources and financing models will be performed. Positive as well as negative externalities will be identified, following by a stakeholder impact analysis to examine how automation affects different stakeholder groups (from the ones identified in D1.2). A sensitivity analysis will be used to test financial resilience under different scenarios. Finally, recommendations on potential implementation strategies, policy measures and mitigation approaches will be proposed. This structured approach will ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the AutoMoTIF automation innovations in real-life conditions, providing valuable insights into economic, business and financial impacts to support informed decision – making.

4.2 Evaluating Impacts on Society

The societal impacts of multimodal automated transportation are significant, particularly in how automation transforms workplace safety and the roles of port workers and logistics operators. Across use cases such as automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels, automated port operations, automated shunting as a service-oriented platform, automated multimodal terminal operations, and seamless integration of automated supply chains, automation has the potential to create safer and more efficient environments.

By reducing reliance on manual labor for high-risk tasks, automation minimizes the likelihood of accidents. For example, automated systems in berthing and port operations handle vessel movements and cargo with precision, reducing the risks associated with human error. Similarly, in shunting and multimodal terminal operations, automation enhances coordination between vehicles and equipment, creating safer conditions for personnel.

Automation also impacts workers by reshaping job roles and improving workplace conditions. Repetitive and physically demanding tasks are replaced by supervisory and technical responsibilities, allowing workers to engage in more fulfilling roles. This shift fosters professional growth as workers acquire new skills, particularly in managing and maintaining advanced automated systems. For instance, the seamless integration of automated supply chains enables logistics operators to focus on decision-making and oversight rather than manual operations.

By enhancing both safety and job quality, automation contributes to a more secure and progressive working environment while maintaining operational efficiency in multimodal freight transport.

4.2.1 Evaluating Societal acceptance

To evaluate the societal acceptance and impact of multimodal freight transport automation, a structured framework is essential. This evaluation can be based on a combination of well-established theories and methodologies, adapting the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and extending it with elements of Socio-Technical Systems Theory. This integrated framework not only measures technical and operational impacts but also incorporates societal, economic, and environmental considerations, providing a holistic assessment of automation in the freight transport sector.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Marangunić and Granić, 2015) serves as the foundation of the evaluation. According to TAM, two primary factors influence the acceptance of technology:

- Perceived Usefulness (PU)
- Perceived Ease of Use (PEU)

PU refers to how much technology is believed to improve efficiency, performance, or quality of life, while PEU relates to how easily users can learn and integrate the technology into their existing systems. These factors are crucial in understanding the willingness of stakeholders to adopt automated solutions, as well as their trust in technology.

To extend TAM, Socio-Technical Systems Theory (Appelbaum, 1997) introduces broader societal and organizational dimensions, which are particularly important when evaluating the impacts of multimodal freight transport automation.

The framework addresses critical societal considerations, such as **Social Norms**, which capture societal expectations about technology adoption, and Trust in Automation, which evaluates public confidence in the reliability, safety, and security of automated systems. **Ethical and Privacy Concerns** are also incorporated, addressing fears related to surveillance, data privacy, and equity. These concerns are especially relevant in automated systems that rely on data collection and processing, particularly for workforce-related information. Additionally, **Workforce Impact** is assessed, focusing on the perceived fairness of automation in terms of job displacement, reskilling opportunities, and changes to labor dynamics in the transport sector.

To measure these impacts, a combination of survey-based metrics and quantitative assessments are used. Survey-based metrics assess public trust in automated systems, willingness to adopt the technology, and perceive fairness in workforce adaptation plans. These surveys provide insights into how stakeholders feel about automation, their confidence in its implementation, and their concerns about its impact on jobs.

The framework also emphasizes qualitative evaluation through focus groups and interviews with key stakeholders, including workers, logistics managers, policymakers, and environmental groups. These discussions allow for a deeper understanding of stakeholders' concerns, such as job displacement, privacy issues, and ethical considerations. Thematic analysis of the feedback gathered from these sessions can reveal the underlying societal barriers to acceptance and provide valuable context to the quantitative data.

4.3 Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative metrics include the reduction in emissions due to automation, cost efficiency improvements (such as cost per ton transported), and safety incident reduction rates. These metrics provide objective data on the operational benefits of automation, such as environmental sustainability and reduced operational costs. Adoption metrics, such as the number of companies or ports adopting automation and the usage rate of automated systems, reflect the technology's market penetration and the broader acceptance by the industry.

4.3.1 Data Collection Approach and KPI Template

The data collection process for this evaluation follows a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data sources to provide a comprehensive assessment of automation in multimodal freight transport.

To ensure consistency and comparability in KPI tracking, a standardized data collection template is used. This template systematically organizes key information for each KPI, facilitating structured reporting and analysis.

Table 7: Template for KPIs collection

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI Name	Description	Target	Data Needed	Data Owner
Unique identifier for the KPI	Relevant impact domain (e.g., Environment, Safety, Society)	Name of the KPI	Explanation of what the KPI measures	Expected performance target or benchmark	Specific data points required to measure the KPI	Entity responsible for providing the data

This structured template ensures that all necessary information is captured uniformly, enabling systematic data collection, validation, and analysis. It also supports efficient data integration across various sources, helping to monitor and compare automation’s impact in different operational contexts.

4.3.2 Comparing Similar KPIs Across Use Cases

A key component of the framework is the cross-use case comparison of similar KPIs, allowing for a targeted assessment of automation’s impact across different operational contexts. This evaluation approach focuses on evaluating specific performance indicators—such as emissions reduction, efficiency gains, safety improvements, and cost savings—across comparable use cases. This targeted comparison enables a deeper understanding of how automation influences key impact areas in different transport settings, such as port-based vs. inland logistics.

By integrating both qualitative and quantitative data, along with theoretical models like the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Socio-Technical Systems Theory, the framework provides a structured approach to evaluating automation’s impact.

The following chapter provides a detailed overview of the selected KPIs for the quantitative analysis.

5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

This chapter provides an overview of the KPIs selected for the quantitative analysis of each UC. Each KPI is briefly described to highlight its purpose and relevance, and the indicators are organized and summarized into a table. The chapter concludes by identifying the common KPIs that have been chosen for cross-sectoral analysis, offering insights into their broader applicability and potential impact across different operational contexts.

It is important to note that these KPIs are preliminary; they may be refined after the simulation phase, when more detailed operational data becomes available. In any case, these KPIs have been selected based on their possibility to be measured before and after the simulation to measure the impact of automated solutions.

5.1 UC1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels

This section presents and discusses the KPIs identified for the automated berthing and unberthing of freight vessels. The outlined KPIs cover several impact areas, i.e., operational efficiency, safety, environment, economy, and society.

The KPI framework for this use case is designed to assess various aspects of the automated system, ensuring a holistic evaluation that covers technical performance, environmental sustainability, economic viability, and societal impact. By leveraging both time-sensitive and resource-specific data, the framework aims to provide actionable insights into the performance of berthing and unberthing processes under varying conditions.

KPIs in Operational Efficiency measure the speed and smoothness of vessel maneuvering and docking. These indicators are critical for understanding how effectively the automated system reduces turnaround times and minimizes disruptions.

- **Manoeuvring and Docking Duration (KPI 1.1):** This KPI measures the time required for a vessel to berth and unberth within the port area. Specifically, it captures the duration of the entire berthing process (i.e., from the anchorage point to being moored at the quay) and the unberthing process (i.e., from the quay to the sailing point). It provides a clear indication of the system's efficiency in reducing turnaround time and streamlining the port call process. Data collection will focus on the duration of operations across different weather conditions, ensuring a comprehensive performance assessment.
- **Number of Tugboat Movements (KPI 1.2):** By tracking the number of directional changes or movements performed by tugboats during the berthing and unberthing processes, this indicator quantifies the operational dynamics. Monitoring these movements under varying weather conditions helps to pinpoint inefficiencies and potential areas for process improvement.

Safety-related metrics focus on the risk exposure for humans involved in berthing and unberthing processes. A key objective is to evaluate whether automation can lower the number of personnel required, thereby potentially reducing humans at risk.

- **Number of Humans at Risk (KPI 1.3):** This safety metric assesses the number of crew members required on tugboats during port calls. The goal is to reduce human involvement in potentially hazardous operations through automation, thereby enhancing overall safety. The KPI is measured by counting the total number of personnel on board tugboats during these operations.

Environmental KPIs monitor the ecological footprint of the operation, including pollutant emissions and energy consumption. These measures help in assessing the sustainability of the automated process under different weather conditions.

- **Amount of Air Pollutant Emissions (KPI 1.4):** This environmental KPI quantifies the emissions produced by both the tugboats and the vessel during berthing and unberthing. Tracking the type and volume of emissions under different weather conditions allows for an assessment of the operation's environmental impact and helps identify areas for improvement.
- **Consumed Energy (KPI 1.5):** Measuring the energy consumption of the tugboats during these operations provides another key environmental metric. The KPI focuses on total fuel consumption, highlighting the energy efficiency of the system and identifying opportunities to optimize fuel usage under various operational conditions.

Economic performance is evaluated by examining operational expenses. This KPI provides insight into the cost efficiency of running the tugboat services during berthing and unberthing, an important factor in overall project feasibility.

- **Operational Expenses of Tugboat Service (KPI 1.6):** This metric tracks the cost associated with operating tugboats during berthing and unberthing. It is essential for evaluating the economic feasibility of the automated system. By monitoring these expenses, stakeholders can perform a detailed cost-benefit analysis to determine the financial viability of the process.

The societal impact is captured by assessing personnel requirements. This metric is crucial for understanding the potential workforce implications of transitioning from conventional to automated operations.

- **Personnel Required (KPI 1.7):** This KPI measures the number of crew members needed to operate the tugboats. It serves as a direct indicator of the potential workforce reduction and improved operational safety that automation might offer. The focus is on determining the optimal crewing levels required for efficient operation under the new automated system.

Table 8: KPIs of UC1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels

KPI ID	Impact area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data owner	Collection tool
1.1	Operational efficiency	Maneuvering and docking duration	The time it takes for the vessel to maneuver and moor once in place at the berth	The time required for berthing and unberthing for various weather conditions	Tugboats shipping company	On site measurements or data provided by the towing services company
1.2	Operational efficiency	Number of tugboat movements	The number of movements each tugboat performs during berthing and unberthing processes	The number of movements (direction changes) a tugboat performs during berthing and unberthing for various weather conditions	Tugboats shipping company	On site measurements or data provided by the towing services company
1.3	Safety	Number of humans at risk	The number of crew required to be onboarded the tugboats during the port call process	The total number of crew on-board the tugboats	Tugboats shipping company	NA
1.4	Environment	Amount of air pollutant emissions	The emissions from the operation of the tugboats and the maneuvered vessel	The type and amount of emissions produced by the tugboats during berthing and unberthing for various weather conditions	Tugboats shipping company	Calculation/estimation through models based on fuel type and consumption
1.5	Environment	Consumed energy	The required amount of energy that each tugboat consumes during berthing and unberthing	The total fuel consumption for berthing and unberthing for various weather conditions	Tugboats shipping company	Calculation/estimation through models based on fuel type and consumption
1.6	Economy	Operational expenses of tugboat service	The operational expenses for operating the tugboats	The cost of operating a tugboat for a berthing and unberthing process	Tugboats shipping company	Data provided by the towing services company
1.7	Society	Personnel required	The number of people (i.e., crew	The number of people required to	Tugboats shipping company	Data provided by the towing services company

KPI ID	Impact area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data owner	Collection tool
			members, operators) required to operate the tugboats	operate the conventional tugboats		

The KPI framework for automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels offers a comprehensive approach to evaluating system performance. It integrates critical aspects of operational efficiency, safety, environmental impact, economic cost, and societal effects. This balanced assessment is intended to guide future improvements and support data-driven decision-making.

As the simulation phase unfolds, these KPIs may be adjusted to better reflect real-world conditions and operational challenges. The structured approach ensures that every key aspect of the operation is measured, helping to validate the benefits of automation while highlighting areas where further optimization may be necessary.

5.2 UC2: Automated port operations

This section introduces and discusses the KPIs that evaluate the performance of automated port operations. These KPIs are related to three primary impact areas: Operations, Environment, and Society.

Operations include a range of time-based and productivity metrics that provide insights into the operational efficiency of the port. From average reception time to berth scheduling efficiency, these KPIs focus on how quickly and effectively cargo is processed and managed throughout its journey in the port. Historical operational time measurements form the backbone of data collection in this area. The operational KPIs provide quantitative measures that are essential for understanding the efficiency and productivity of port operations. They include:

- Average Reception, Inspection, and Transfer Times (KPIs 2.1 to 2.3): These indicators measure the time elapsed during critical stages of cargo handling. By using historical data, these KPIs offer benchmarks against which the performance of automated systems can be compared. Shorter processing times are indicative of improved efficiency and may lead to higher throughput and reduced congestion.
- Time to Warehouse and Storage (KPIs 2.4 and 2.5): These metrics track the progression of cargo from vessel arrival to final storage. They are essential for identifying any delays or bottlenecks that may occur between different stages of the port operation.
- Waiting Time and Global Productivity Index (KPIs 2.6 and 2.7): While waiting time highlights potential inefficiencies, the Global Productivity Index—measured in terms of the number of cargo units handled per shift—serves as a key performance driver that directly influences overall operational output.
- Utilization and Response Metrics (KPIs 2.8 and 2.9): The utilization rate for machinery and operators provides insights into resource allocation and effectiveness, whereas the average resource

response time measures how quickly a request for a resource is fulfilled. These indicators help to assess the operational readiness and flexibility of the automated system.

- Berth Utilization and Scheduling Efficiency (KPIs 2.10 and 2.11): These KPIs evaluate the effective use of port berths. By comparing actual berth occupancy with planned usage, these metrics are instrumental in identifying and mitigating operational delays, ultimately ensuring that berth resources are optimally deployed.

Environment: Environmental KPIs evaluate the ecological footprint of port activities. They assess parameters such as CO₂ emissions and energy consumption rates during port cycles. These measurements integrate data from both ground vehicles and vessel operations, reflecting the total environmental cost associated with each operational cycle.

- CO₂ Emission and Port Energy Consumption (KPIs 2.12 and 2.13): Environmental sustainability is a critical for modern port operations. These indicators quantify the ecological impact by measuring emissions and energy usage during the operational cycle. The integration of diverse data points—such as fuel consumption and vehicle power ratings—ensures a detailed assessment of environmental performance.

Society: The societal impact of automation is captured through subjective measures. These include perceptions of usefulness and ease of use, as well as workforce concerns regarding privacy and job security. Although these KPIs are not based on direct operational metrics, they are crucial in assessing the broader acceptance and potential challenges of integrating automated systems within the port environment.

- Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use (KPIs 2.14 and 2.15): These subjective measures capture how the technology is viewed by its end users, reflecting the perceived improvements in efficiency and overall system integration. These KPIs provide valuable insights into user acceptance and can guide further refinements to enhance system usability.
- Privacy Impact and Expendability Indices (KPIs 2.16 and 2.17): Addressing societal concerns, these metrics measure the perceived risks related to personal data handling and job security. By quantifying workforce sentiment, these KPIs help port management to understand and mitigate any negative perceptions of automation, thus ensuring smoother transitions during technological upgrades.

Table 9: KPIs of UC2: Automated port operations

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection Tool
2.1	Operations	Avg. Reception time	Time elapsed in the reception of the cargo. This covers from the beginning of the unloading to the end of the loading.	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection Tool
2.2	Operations	Avg. Cargo inspection time	Time taken for the inspection of the cargo	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.3	Operations	Avg. Transfer time	Total time of cargo transfer among port facilities	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.4	Operations	Avg. time to warehouse	Time spent from the arrival of the vessel until the cargo enters the warehouse	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.5	Operations	Avg. time to storage	Time elapsed from entering the warehouse until all the load is stored in its assigned location	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.6	Operations	Avg. Waiting time	Total waiting time per cycle	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.7	Operations	Global Productivity Index	Number of cargo units handled per shift	Historical operational time measurements	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.8	Operations	Utilization rate	It relates the total time that a machine is in service and the total cycle time. This is done for each type of machine and operator.	How long each machine is on duty from the arrival of the ship until final storage OR Percentage of service time	N/A	Through simulation
2.9	Operations	Avg. Resource response time	Average time spent from the request of a resource until the moment the resource is working in the process	N/A	N/A	Through simulation
2.10	Operations	Berth utilization rate	Measures the efficiency of berth usage by comparing the time a berth is occupied to the total available berth time. Indicates how effectively the port is utilizing its berths	Measurements of berth occupancy time or percentage of use per day	N/A	Historical records
2.11	Operations	Berth Scheduling Efficiency (BSE)	Measures efficiency of berth usage against plan and delays	Measurements of berth occupancy time or percentage of use per day + planning	N/A	Historical records

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection Tool
2.12	Environment	CO2 emission	Total CO2 amount emitted throughout a whole cycle (ground vehicles + vessel anchorage & berthing)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground vehicles travelled distance (km) • Ground vehicle fuel consumption (L/km) • Fuel Type • Vessel auxiliary motor power (KW) • Vessel specific fuel consumption (g fuel / KWh) 	N/A	Historical records + technical specifications
2.13	Environment	Port energy consumption rate	Total amount of energy consumed in a complete cycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground vehicles travelled distance (km) • Ground vehicle fuel consumption (L/km) • Fuel Type • Vessel auxiliary motor power (KW) • Vessel specific fuel consumption (g fuel / KWh) 	N/A	Historical records + technical specifications
2.14	Society	Perceived Usefulness	The extent to which technology is seen as improving efficiency, performance, or quality of life.	N/A	N/A	Qualitative Survey
2.15	Society	Perceived Ease of Use	How easy technology is to learn and integrate into existing systems.	N/A	N/A	Qualitative Survey
2.16	Society	Privacy Impact Index	Measures workforce concern about how automated systems handle personal/work data	N/A	N/A	Qualitative Survey
2.17	Society	Perceived Expendability index	Measures workforce perception of to what extent automation threatens their job	N/A	N/A	On site measurements & Expertise estimation
2.18	Safety	Number of humans at risk	Number of people required	NA	NA	NA

Table 9 presents and overview KPI table is a critical component of the evaluation framework for automated port operations. While it offers a detailed roadmap for performance measurement, the reliance on historical operational data and the necessity for condition-specific information underscore the importance of a rigorous data collection process. As the simulation phase progresses, refinements to these KPIs may be required to better align with actual operational conditions and to capture emerging trends and challenges.

This multidimensional approach not only provides a comprehensive assessment of operational efficiency but also integrates environmental and societal perspectives, ensuring that the transition to automation is both sustainable and socially responsible.

5.3 UC3: Automated Shunting as a Service oriented platform

This chapter introduces and examines the KPIs developed for the automated shunting service platform. The table presents a broad range of KPIs that span various impact areas—including economy, environment, interoperability, operations, safety, and society. As with other use cases, these KPIs may be refined after the simulation phase when more detailed operational insights become available.

The KPI framework for the automated shunting service platform is designed to capture both the technical and operational performance of the system, as well as its broader economic, environmental, and societal implications. By addressing these diverse aspects, the framework ensures that the evaluation of the platform is balanced and multidimensional.

Economic KPIs (3.1, 3.2, and 3.3) measure various facets of cost efficiency and productivity. Metrics such as capital productivity, energy costs per TEU, and labor productivity help quantify the economic benefits of the automated system relative to the volume of cargo handled.

- Capital Productivity (KPI 3.1): This metric evaluates the efficiency of capital utilization by dividing the capital employed by the number of TEUs handled. It offers insights into how effectively the invested capital translates into cargo throughput.
- Energy Costs (KPI 3.2): By calculating energy costs on a per-TEU basis, this KPI provides a clear measure of the operational expenses related to fuel and electricity consumption. This helps in assessing the cost-effectiveness of the shunting process.
- Labor Productivity (KPI 3.3): This indicator measures work hours required per TEU handled, offering a view on labor efficiency. It serves as an important metric for understanding how automation might optimize workforce utilization.
- Environmental performance is tracked via KPIs 3.4 and 3.5. These indicators focus on the ecological footprint of operations by measuring CO₂-equivalent emissions and energy consumption on a per-TEU basis. They require detailed data on fuel and electricity consumption to ensure a precise evaluation of environmental impact.
- CO₂ Emissions (KPI 3.4): This KPI quantifies the greenhouse gas emissions generated per TEU, considering both diesel and electricity usage. It is a critical measure for assessing the environmental sustainability of the operations.
- Energy Consumption (KPI 3.5): Focusing on energy consumption per TEU, this metric leverages data on fuel and electricity usage to evaluate the overall energy efficiency of the system. Lower energy consumption per unit of cargo indicates a more sustainable operation.

A series of KPIs (3.6 through 3.14) focuses on operational performance. These indicators cover aspects from resource idle time and train travel times to turnaround times, loading/unloading durations, and overall track occupancy. They provide a comprehensive view of how efficiently the system handles shunting operations.

- Average Idle Time (KPI 3.6): This metric measures the average idle time per TEU processed, providing insights into potential inefficiencies in the system. It is key to identifying areas where operational downtime can be minimized.
- Train Travel and Turnaround Times (KPIs 3.8 – 3.12): These indicators measure various aspects of train operations, including inbound and outbound travel times, turnaround times, and loading/unloading durations. They are crucial for evaluating the overall efficiency of train movements within the terminal.
- TEUs Handled (KPI 3.13): A straightforward yet essential metric, this KPI tracks the total number of TEUs processed by the system, serving as a direct measure of operational throughput.
- Infrastructure Usage (KPI 3.14): This metric measures track occupancy rates, indicating how effectively the terminal's infrastructure is being utilized during operations.
- Safety: KPI 3.15 monitors safety by evaluating accident rates relative to the volume of cargo handled. This metric is essential for understanding how automation contributes to safer operational environments.
- Accident Reduction (KPI 3.15): By measuring the number of accidents per TEU handled, this KPI provides an important indicator of the safety improvements achieved through automation. A reduction in accidents reflects positively on both system reliability and operator safety.
- Society: KPI 3.16 addresses the societal impact by tracking the number of personnel required. This metric is crucial in the context of automation, as it highlights potential changes in workforce requirements and supports an analysis of social implications.
- Personnel Required (KPI 3.16): This KPI evaluates the human resource aspect by tracking the number of personnel needed to operate the system. It offers valuable insights into the workforce impact of automation and helps inform planning for current and future scenarios.

Table 10: KPIs of UC3: Automated Shunting as a Service oriented platform

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection Tool
3.1	Economy	Capital productivity	Capital employed/TEU handled (€/TEU)	Capital invested	MIS	NA
				Number of TEUs handled		
3.2	Economy	Energy costs	Costs derived from the consumption of energy (€/TEU)	Diesel and electricity costs	MIS	NA
				Number of TEUs handled		
3.3	Economy/societal	Labor productivity		Work hours	MIS	NA

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection Tool
			Work hours/TEU handled (t/TEU; €/TEU)	Number of TEUs handled		
3.4	Environment	CO2e emissions**	kg CO2/TEU	Diesel and electricity costs	MIS	NA
				Number of TEUs handled		
3.5	Environment	Energy consumption	Kj/TEU	Diesel and electricity consumption	MIS	NA
				Number of TEUs handled		
3.6	Operations	Average idle time	Average idle time per TEU processed (t/TEU)	Idle time of ITUs (in TEUs)	MIS	NA
3.7	Operations	Average travel train (inbound)	Average time from leaving the station to the arrival in the terminal (t)	Train departure time from the track in the station	MIS	NA
				Train arrival time at the track in the terminal		
3.8	Operations	Average travel train (outbound)	Average time from leaving the terminal to arriving in the station (t)	Train departure time from the track at the terminal	MIS	NA
				Train arrival time at the track in the station		
3.9	Operations	Average train turnaround time (inbound)	Average time required for a train to complete operations from entering the terminal until being ready for unload (t/m)	Train arrival time at the terminal	MIS	NA
				Time of train being ready for unloading		
				Length of the train		
3.10	Operations	Average train turnaround time (outbound)	Average time required for a train to complete operations from being loaded until	Time of train being loaded	MIS	NA
				Train departure time from the terminal		

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection Tool
			leaving the terminal (t/m)	Length of the train		
3.11	Operations	Train unloading duration (inbound)	The average time needed from the train being ready to be unloaded until the train is fully unloaded (t/TEU)	Time train ready for unloading	MIS	NA
				Completion time of unloading		
				Number of TEUs		
3.12	Operations	Train loading duration (outbound)	The average time needed from the train being ready to be loaded until the train is fully loaded (t/TEU)	Time train ready for loading	MIS	NA
				Completion time of loading		
				Number of TEUs		
3.13	Operations	TEUs handled	Number of TEUs handled (TEU/t)	Number of TEUs	MIS	NA
3.14	Operations	Infrastructure usage	Track occupancy rate (%)	Time load/unload tracks are occupied	MIS	NA
3.15	Safety	Accident reduction	Number of accidents/TEU handled (n/TEU)	Number of accidents	MIS	NA
				TEUs handled		
3.16	Society	Number of humans at risk	Absolute number of personnel required for current and future scenarios (n)	Number of people working in the terminal	MIS	NA

The KPI table for the automated shunting service platform represents a comprehensive approach to performance evaluation. By integrating metrics across security, economic, environmental, operational, safety, and societal domains, the framework ensures a holistic assessment of the platform's effectiveness. Data-driven insights will be critical, particularly as the simulation phase provides more detailed operational feedback that may necessitate adjustments to these KPIs.

As the project evolves, further refinement of the undefined metrics in (cyber-)security and interoperability will be essential. Overall, this KPI framework lays a solid foundation for understanding and optimizing the performance of an automated, service-oriented shunting system in a modern, integrated transport environment.

5.4 UC4: Automated multimodal terminal operations

This chapter introduces and analyzes the KPIs developed for automated multimodal terminal operations. The Table 11 covers a range of metrics across environmental, operational, safety, societal, and economic impact areas. It is important to note that these KPIs are provisional and may be refined after the simulation phase when more detailed process data becomes available.

Environmental Impact Metrics in this area assess energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions associated with terminal operations.

- Average Power Usage per Container Move (KPI 4.1): This KPI measures the average power required to move a container from the yard to the rail. It involves tracking the energy consumption per move for each type of machinery, helping to assess the energy efficiency of the container handling process.
- CO₂ Emissions (KPI 4.2): Monitoring CO₂ emissions released within a specific timeframe (e.g., monthly) provides insight into the terminal's environmental footprint. This KPI uses annual CO₂ emission data to establish benchmarks and track improvements over time.

Operational Efficiency: These KPIs measure the effectiveness and speed of container handling, train operations, and yard utilization.

- Average Container Handling Time – Discharge (KPI 4.3): This metric captures the average time required to discharge a container from a train and place it into its designated yard slot. It relies on the precise recording of the time at which the container is discharged and when it is positioned in the yard.
- Average Container Handling Time – Loading (KPI 4.4): Like discharge time, this KPI measures the time required to load a container from the yard onto a train. It is critical for identifying potential bottlenecks and improving the overall loading process.
- Average Train Turnaround Time (KPI 4.5): This KPI evaluates the efficiency of train operations by measuring the time from the initiation of rail operations to their completion. Reducing turnaround time is key to enhancing terminal throughput.
- Yard Block Utilization (KPI 4.6): Yard block utilization assesses how effectively the yard space is used within a specific period. By considering container dwell time, total yard block slots, and the number of containers handled, this KPI helps optimize space and improve operational planning.
- ASC Utilization (KPI 4.7): This metric measures the utilization rate of Automated Stacking Cranes (ASCs) within a given timeframe. It is calculated by comparing the total time of ASC availability (during a shift) against idle time, providing insights into equipment efficiency.
- Average Handling Moves per Discharged Container (KPI 4.8) and per Loading Container (KPI 4.9): These KPIs evaluate the operational efficiency by determining the average number of handlings required for discharging and loading containers, respectively. They highlight the complexity and potential inefficiencies in container movement processes.

- Container Dwell Time (KPI 4.10): Measuring the time a container remains in the yard until it is loaded on a train, this KPI is a direct indicator of yard efficiency and inventory management.

Safety: Safety is evaluated through indicators such as accident rates, which provide insight into the overall risk profile of terminal operations.

- Accident Rate (KPI 4.11): This KPI tracks the number of accidents—both fatal and non-fatal—occurring within a specified timeframe, typically on an annual basis. A lower accident rate reflects improved safety measures and more effective risk management.

Societal Impact: Metrics under this domain evaluate workforce requirements and the broader human implications of automation.

- Personnel Required (KPI 4.12): This indicator measures the average number of personnel required for train operations. It provides insight into labor needs and helps assess the impact of automation on workforce requirements.

Economic Performance: Economic KPIs focus on the cost efficiency of operations, particularly personnel-related expenses.

- Personnel Average Cost per Container Loading (KPI 4.13): By calculating the average personnel cost required to load a container onto a train, this KPI offers a view of the economic efficiency of labor utilization. It considers both the number of people assigned to rail operations and their average salaries, providing a clear measure of cost efficiency.

Table 11: KPIs of UC4: Automated multimodal terminal operations

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection tool
4.1	Environment	average power usage per container move yard to rail	The average power required for a container to be moved from yard to the respective wagon	The power consumed per move per machinery type	NTB	NA
4.2	Environment	CO2 emissions	CO2 emissions released within a specific timeframe (suggested month)	CO2 emissions produced by the terminal on a yearly basis	NTB	NA
4.3	Operations	average container handling time - discharge	The average time required for a container to be discharged from a wagon and placed in the proper yard slot	Time of container discharge Time of container placed in the yard	NTB	NA
4.4	Operations	average container handling time - loading	The average time required for a container to be loaded from a wagon and placed in the proper yard slot	Time of container loading Time of container placed on the respective wagon	NTB	NA

KPI ID	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data needed	Data Owner	Collection tool
4.5	Operations	average train turnaround time	The average time required for a train to complete operations	Time of initiation of rail operations Time of completion of rail operations	NTB	NA
4.6	Operations	Yard block - utilization	The yard block utilization within a specific timeframe (suggested month)	Container dwell time Number of total yard block slots Number of containers handled in the yard block	NTB	NA
4.7	Operations	ASC utilization	The utilization of an ASC within a specific timeframe (suggested month)	Total time of ASC availability (assigned to a shift) Total time of idling (within the assigned shift)	NTB	NA
4.8	Operations	Average handling moves per discharged container	The average number of handlings moves a container requires for discharging from a train	Number of handlings moves for a container from the wagon to the yard	NTB	NA
4.9	Operations	Average handling moves per loading container	The average number of handlings a container requires for loading to a train	Number of handlings moves for a container from the yard to the wagon and vice versa	NTB	NA
4.10	Operations	Container dwell time	The average time a container stays in the yard until it is loaded on the train.	Time of container entering the yard Time of container loaded on rail	NTB	NA
4.11	Safety	Accident rate	The number of accidents occurred in a specific timeframe fatal and non-fatal (suggested year)	Number of accidents on a yearly basis	NTB	NA
4.12	Society	Number of humans at risk	Average number of personnel required for train operations	The number of people assigned to rail operations	NTB	NA
4.13	Economy	Personnel average cost per container loading	The average personnel cost required to load a container onto a train	The number of people assigned at the rail operations The average salary of the assigned personnel	NTB	NA

The KPI framework for automated multimodal terminal operations provides a comprehensive and multidimensional approach to evaluating terminal performance. By integrating metrics across environmental, operational, safety, societal, and economic domains, this framework facilitates a balanced assessment of how automation affects terminal efficiency and sustainability.

This comprehensive KPI framework lays a solid foundation for understanding and optimizing automated multimodal terminal operations, driving improvements that are both effective and sustainable in a modern terminal environment.

5.5 Comparison of KPIs across UCs

Table 12 presents a comparative summary of KPIs across different UCs in multimodal freight transport automation. By consolidating similar KPIs from various UCs, the table highlights common impact areas such as operations, safety, environment, economy, and society. This structured comparison enables a better understanding of how automation influences different aspects of freight transport, ensuring consistency in evaluation and facilitating cross-use case benchmarking.

Table 12: Comparative Summary of KPIs across different UCs

KPI ID (UC Ref.)	Impact Area	KPI	Description	Data Needed
1.1, 2.1, 3.6, 4.3, 4.4	Operational Efficiency	Handling Time	Time required for various handling operations (berthing, cargo transfer, shunting, etc.)	Time measurements
1.2, 2.10, 2.11	Operational Efficiency	Berth/Infrastructure Utilization	Efficiency of berth or infrastructure usage over time	Berth occupancy time, planning data
1.3, 2.16, 2.18, 3.15, 3.16, 4.11, 4.12	Safety	Accident Rate / Number of Humans at Risk	Frequency of accidents or personnel exposed to risk during operations	Accident reports, personnel data
1.4, 2.12, 3.4, 4.2	Environmental Impact	CO2 Emissions	Total emissions produced during operations (vessels, vehicles, terminals)	Fuel consumption, energy use data
1.5, 2.13, 3.5, 4.1	Environmental Impact	Energy Consumption	Energy required for specific operations (container moves, berthing, etc.)	Power usage per process
1.6, 3.1, 3.2, 4.13	Economic Impact	Operational / Personnel Cost	Costs associated with operations, including labor and energy	Salary, energy costs, operational expenses
1.7, 2.16, 3.16, 4.12	Society	Number of humans at risk	Number of personnel required for various operational tasks	Workforce allocation data
2.6, 3.6	Operational Efficiency	Waiting / Idle Time	Time spent waiting for operations to proceed	Operational time measurements

This comparative analysis of KPIs across use cases provides valuable insights into the shared and distinct impacts of automation in multimodal freight transport. By aligning similar KPIs, the table supports a more comprehensive evaluation, helping stakeholders identify trends, best practices, and potential areas for improvement. This harmonized approach ensures that the assessment framework remains consistent, robust, and adaptable to various operational contexts, ultimately contributing to a more efficient and sustainable transport system.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined a comprehensive evaluation framework that integrates multiple dimensions to assess the impact of automation in multimodal freight transport. We began with a state-of-the-art analysis, examining relevant EU projects and their evaluation methodologies, as well as the KPIs they employed. This review provided a solid foundation for the development of our own evaluation approach.

Based on this analysis, we proposed a structured evaluation methodology centered on a set of quantitative KPIs. These KPIs were carefully selected by the use case (UC) participants, under the guidance of an appointed evaluation leader for each UC. The selection process considered several key factors: alignment with impact areas defined in the grant agreement and further described in this deliverable based on the findings of D1.2, insights from the state-of-the-art review, and the ability to measure each KPI both before and after simulations to determine the effect of automation.

In addition to the KPI-based evaluation, the framework introduces preliminary approaches for assessing social impacts (to be further developed in T3.5), conducting financial and economic feasibility analysis (planned for T3.4), and evaluating interoperability and cybersecurity aspects (to be addressed in T3.3). These components ensure a holistic assessment that goes beyond operational efficiency to include societal, economic, and technical considerations.

Furthermore, this deliverable has presented a structured approach to comparing KPIs across different use cases. By aligning similar KPIs, we enable a cross-pilot evaluation that provides a broader understanding of the impact of automation across various contexts. This comparison will be instrumental in drawing overarching conclusions on the benefits and challenges of automation in multimodal freight transport.

In summary, the proposed evaluation framework lays a solid groundwork for assessing automation's effectiveness, efficiency, and societal implications. Future tasks will refine these methodologies, ensuring a comprehensive and actionable evaluation of automation's role in freight transport innovation.

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